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The Positive Judgment on Future Prospects in the Italian Regions During the Period 2012-2022

It grew by an average of 18.91% between 2012 and 2022

Istat calculates the value of the positive opinion on future prospects. The variable is calculated as the percentage of people aged 14 and over who believe that their personal situation will improve in the next 5 years out of the total number of people aged 14 and over. The data refers to the Italian regions between 2012 and 2022.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of positive opinion on future prospects in 2022. Sardinia is in first place by value of positive opinion on future prospects in 2022 with an amount equal to 34.1 units, followed by Lombardy with an amount equal to 32.7, and from Lazio with a value of 32.1. In the middle of the table are Friuli Venezia Giulia with a value of 29 units, followed by Piedmont and Tuscany with a value of 28.7 units. The Marche closes the ranking with a value of 25.3 units, followed by Calabria with a value of 24.8 units and Sicily with a value of 24.7 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in the positive opinion on future prospects between 2012 and 2022. Campania is in first place by value of the percentage change in the positive opinion on future prospects with a value equal to 44.5% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 20.9 units up to a value of 30.2 units or corresponding to a variation of 9.3 units. Puglia follows with a variation equal to an amount of 43.72% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 19.9 units up to a value of 28.6 units equal to +8.7 units. In third place, there is Liguria with a value equal to +40.51% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 19.5 units up to a value of 27.4 units equal to an amount of +7.9 units. In the middle of the ranking there is Tuscany with a value equal to +26.43% corresponding to an amount from 22.7 units up to a value of 28.7 units equal to a value of 6 units. Sicily follows with a variation equal to an amount of 25.38% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 19.7 units up to a value of 24.7 units. In eleventh place is Basilicata with a variation equal to +25.2% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 24.6 units up to a value of 30.8 units. Veneto closes the ranking with a variation of 0.00%. Calabria follows with a variation of -2.36% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 25.4 units up to 24.8 units. Finally, Umbria is in last place with a variation equal to -5.05% corresponding to a variation from 27.7 units up to 26.3 units. On average, the value of the positive opinion on future prospects grew by 18.91% for the Italian regions, going from 24.19 to 28.76.

Positive opinion on future prospects in the Italian macro regions. The positive opinion on future prospects in the Italian macro-regions has grown in all Italian macro-regions. Specifically, this value grew in the North by an amount equal to 10.29%, in the North-West by an amount equal to +11.51%, in the North-East by an amount of 9.13%, in the Center by value equal to 24.17%, in the South for an amount equal to +31.48%, in the South with 33.64% and in the Islands for a value equal to 26.64%.

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Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified as indicated below:

- Cluster 1: Lombardy, Veneto, Sardinia, Lazio, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Valle d'Aosta, Emilia Romagna;
- Cluster 2: Puglia, Liguria, Sicily, Molise, Marche, Calabria, Piedmont, Tuscany, Campania, Umbria, Basilicata, Trentino Alto Adige, Abruzzo.

From the point of view of the trend of the clusters we can note that the average value of cluster 1 is higher than the average value of cluster 2. The following ordering therefore derives: $C1 > C2$. We can note that both clusters are heterogeneous, that is, they are made up of regions that have very different socio-economic and geographical conditions. In fact, it is not possible to identify groupings by per capita income, by belonging to geographical macro-regions, or by level of socio-cultural development. It therefore follows that setting the value of $k=2$, although optimal from the point of view of the Silhouette coefficient, is insufficient in the sense of identifying groups that can make sense from a socio-economic point of view. For this motivation we set a value of $k=3$. By setting $k=3$, even knowing that this is a sub-optimal value, it is possible to obtain the following clustering:

- Cluster 1: Lombardy, Sardinia, Veneto, Valle d'Aosta, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Lazio, Emilia Romagna;
- Cluster 2: Liguria, Sicily, Puglia, Molise, Marche;
- Cluster 3: Basilicata, Trentino Alto Adige, Umbria, Tuscany, Abruzzo, Piedmont, Calabria, Campania.

We can note that from the point of view of the ordering of the clusters based on the average value of the positive opinion on future prospects, the following ordering results: $C1 > C3 > C2$. However, even in this case, i.e. with $k=3$, as in the previous one with $k=2$, it is not possible to identify a structure of the groupings that can be homogeneous from a socio-economic or geographical point of view. The clusters remain in the heterogeneity dimension. For example, in Cluster 1, together with some regions with high per capita income such as Lombardy and Veneto, there is also Sardinia and Lazio. In Cluster 3 the level of heterogeneity is even higher as together with Trentino Alto Adige we also find Abruzzo, Campania, Piedmont and Basilicata. Finally, cluster 2 is also characterized by heterogeneity.

The analysis therefore shows a rather paradoxical condition characterized by the fact that regions that have very different per capita incomes and socio-cultural conditions from each other have the ability to express the same level of positive judgment on future prospects. In this regard, it is useful to remember that people who have low per capita incomes often tend to lie about their expectations, positively exaggerating them, and people who have medium-high per capita incomes tend to underestimate their expectations.

Conclusions. We can note that the value of the positive opinion on future prospects grew in all regions between 2012 and 2022 with the exception of Calabria, Umbria and Veneto. We can also note that the value of the positive opinion on future prospects improved in all Italian macro-regions between 2012 and 2022. However, on average, in 2022 only 28.7% of the Italian population expressed a positive opinion on future perspectives. It follows that the vast majority of the population lacks this positive expectation. Certainly, the indicator analyzed shows an increasing trend. However, only 1 in 3 Italians has positive opinions on future prospects.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

Macro-Regioni	2012	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
<i>Nord</i>	27,2	30	2,8	10,29
<i>Nord-ovest</i>	27,8	31	3,2	11,51
<i>Nord-est</i>	26,3	28,7	2,4	9,13
<i>Centro</i>	24	29,8	5,8	24,17
<i>Mezzogiorno</i>	21,6	28,4	6,8	31,48
<i>Sud</i>	21,7	29	7,3	33,64
<i>Isole</i>	21,4	27,1	5,7	26,64

Regione	2012	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Piemonte	21,7	28,7	7,00	32,26
Valle d'Aosta	23,8	27,8	4,00	16,81
Liguria	19,5	27,4	7,90	40,51
Lombardia	32	32,7	0,70	2,19
Trentino-Alto Adige	22,8	30,6	7,80	34,21
Veneto	29	29	0,00	0,00
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	27,2	29	1,80	6,62
Emilia-Romagna	24	27,8	3,80	15,83
Toscana	22,7	28,7	6,00	26,43
Umbria	27,7	26,3	-1,40	-5,05
Marche	24,1	25,3	1,20	4,98
Lazio	24,3	32,1	7,80	32,10
Abruzzo	22,9	31,2	8,30	36,24
Molise	25	25,5	0,50	2,00
Campania	20,9	30,2	9,30	44,50
Puglia	19,9	28,6	8,70	43,72
Basilicata	24,6	30,8	6,20	25,20
Calabria	25,4	24,8	-0,60	-2,36
Sicilia	19,7	24,7	5,00	25,38
Sardegna	26,6	34,1	7,50	28,20

